

EXPLORING AWARENESS AND ATTITUDE AMONG NURSES TOWARDS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN FATIMA MEMORIAL HOSPITAL LAHORE PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare holds promise to address these issues by integrating real-world data-driven insights into patient care processes. Globally, healthcare systems strive to provide the highest quality of care at a reasonable cost while guaranteeing widespread access for all populations.

Objective: The study aims to assess the attitude and level of awareness among nurses toward AI.

Material and Method: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted across the Fatima Memorial Hospital in Lahore, Pakistan to gather insights from nurses regarding AI. Data collection occurred within three-month period using an adapted structured questionnaire. The study sample included 171 registered nurses, each with at least one year of clinical experience, selected through convenience sampling. The survey was divided into three key sections: demographic data, an evaluation of participants' knowledge about artificial intelligence, and a scale measuring their general attitudes toward AI.

Results: Nurses displayed "High awareness" toward AI technology, with 95.3% having basic information about AI and only 74.3% (127 nurses) were considered "aware" of AI as they dealt with one of its healthcare applications. 49.1% Nurses expressed openness to AI integration on one side, but also had some concerns about AI. Nurses expressed conservative attitudes toward AI, with significant differences observed based on years of nursing experience ($\chi^2 = 8.07, p < 0.05$). However, other demographic characteristics did not reveal significant variations in attitudes.

Conclusion: Healthcare leaders should boost nurses' AI awareness and promote its integration into practice. Addressing concerns about AI control, especially across generations, as younger nurses are generally more tech-positive is essential. Change management can help to ease adoption barriers.

INTRODUCTION

Ambulance personnel face challenging circumstances when responding to crises, including possibly dangerous situations or circumstances that are exceedingly physically

and mentally taxing. According to Aasland et al. [1] and Jackson et al. [2], there is a natural risk to their well-being in this particular work environment, which raises worries about rising

stress, burnout, and compromised mental health. Both their emotional and physical health may be impacted by this. According to Lawn et al. [3], ambulance workers who are under stress at work often feel let down by their superiors, colleagues, and the organization itself. This is especially true when they are unwell and coming to work. This contributes to work-related stress in the emergency medical industry including shift work, recurrent exposure to traumatic events, and stressors related to leadership and organization [4]. As a result, there is a risk that their specific work environment may have a negative impact on their mental health and lead to increased stress, burnout, and diminished well-being. As such, there is a need to enhance their well-being and job longevity by cultivating emotional intelligence [5] addressing stress and maintaining their work-life balance.

The American Psychological Association (APA) [6], defined stress as the "body's response to any demand". In this case, the ambulance personnel could experience different forms of stress as they are dealing with emergency cases and distressing accidents. According to Hanes and Shalev [7], long-term stress can cause a host of detrimental health effects, such as anxiety, depression, burnout, and even physical conditions like cardiovascular disease. On the other hand, Salovey and Mayer [8] defined emotional intelligence (EI) as "the ability to perceive, understand, use, and manage one's own emotions in positive ways to achieve one's goals", EI equips individuals with the skills to cope with stress effectively. These skills include self-awareness, emotional regulation, empathy, and social awareness, allowing them to manage their own emotional responses, build rapport with patients and colleagues, and navigate interpersonal dynamics effectively [9]. On the other context, the demands of the work of the ambulance personnel could lead to erratic equilibrium which had an adverse effect with the balance creating an imbalance between work and personal life. Work-life balance refers to the "integration of the various roles that an individual has, such as those of worker, family member, friend, and citizen, in a way that he or she finds personally fulfilling and satisfying" [10]. For ambulance personnel, long hours,

irregular schedules, and emotional toll can erode this balance, leading to decreased job satisfaction, family conflict, and impaired personal well-being [11].

The capacity to comprehend and regulate not just our own feelings but also those of people around us is what is known as emotional intelligence, or emotional intelligence (EI). Self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills are the five elements that make up emotional intelligence. Being fully cognizant of one's own personality, including its motivations, ideas, feelings, and strengths and shortcomings, is the definition of self-awareness. Understanding oneself enables one to comprehend others as well, including how they see you, your attitude toward them, and your immediate reactions [12]. Resilience, which has to do with a person's capacity to handle stress, is another crucial component of the well-being of emergency personnel. Organizational support, informal support, use of humor, and individual ways to cope such as detachment and external supports are some of the well-being needs expressed by ambulance staff [13]. Inadequate leadership is one of the most stressful aspects of the job for ambulance personnel [14].

For ambulance workers, work-life balance is a "context-sensitive and subjective concept" that varies according on personal preferences, life phases, and situations [15]. As such, it cannot be adequately defined. The specific elements of ambulance job pose substantial hurdles to work-life balance [16]. Working long hours, having erratic schedules, working shifts, experiencing trauma, and making difficult decisions under pressure can often cause personal life disruption and make it difficult to distinguish between work and personal life. Work-life balance is a dynamic process that requires constant modification and effort rather than a static destination [17]. This comprehension enables flexibility in identifying unique demands and considering multiple options to preserve equilibrium throughout an emergency medical professional's career.

Understanding the complex interplay between these factors is crucial to promoting the well-being and resilience of ambulance personnel.

This study delves into this intricate web, investigating how stress, emotional intelligence, and work-life balance interact and influence the professional and personal lives of these vital members of the emergency medical services. Through this exploration, this study identifies strategies and interventions that can empower ambulance personnel to navigate the challenges of their work while maintaining their mental and physical health, achieving a sense of fulfilment in both their professional and personal domains. To this end, this study aimed to investigate the interplay of stress, emotional intelligence, and work-life balance among ambulance personnel.

Materials and methods

Research Design

A descriptive correlational study was adopted to investigate the interplay of stress, emotional intelligence, and work-life balance among the Ambulance Personnel through a convenient sampling technique using a survey approach.

Participants

Participants were paramedics from two regional ambulance services of Pakistan (i.e. Karachi and Hyderabad, Sindh). Inclusion criteria include Pakistani Nationality, male paramedics working in the ambulance for at least two years, and holding a paramedic license or equivalent. Excluded were those who had just joined the workforce and the ambulance drivers.

The number of samples was determined using Rao software's online sample calculator. The 95% confidence interval for the standard deviation was chosen. The response distribution was 50% and the margin of error was + 5%. The recommended sample size was 140. However, only 120 completed the questionnaire. The study was conducted over 3 months from April 2023 to June 2023. The data collection was done after obtaining ethical permission from the concerned authorities and the Institutional Ethics Committee of King Khalid University (ECM#2023-1906).

Questionnaire

A self-assessment questionnaire was administered online. Data were collected by using predetermined tools.

The perceived stress scale (PSS - 10) developed by Cohen, Kamarch, & Mermelstein, 1983 was used for measuring stress. Individual scores on the PSS can range from 0 to 40 with higher scores indicating higher perceived. Scores ranging from (0-13) would be considered low stress, (14-26) moderate stress, and (27-40) high perceived stress [18]. The Cronbach's alpha of the PSS-10 was 0.80.

The Schutte Self Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT 2011) by Schutte and Malouff [19] was also used in this study. It consisted of 33 items each with five responses such as strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree, and rated from 1 to 5. There are four subcomponents: Perception of Emotion, (10-50), Managing own

Emotions (9-45) Managing others' Emotions (8-40), and Utilization of Emotion (6-30) with a total obtainable score of 33-165. The reliability of this questionnaire revealed a Cronbach's alpha of 0.89.

Lastly, the Work/Life Balance Self-Assessment scale developed by Smeltzer SC [20] has 15 items with total obtainable scores of 15-75, addresses three factors such as work interference with personal life (WIPL) (7-35) (personal life interference with work (PLIW) (4-20), and work/personal life enhancement (WPLE) (4-20). The content validity and reliability of the questionnaire were evaluated in a previous study [21] however, in this current study, the reliability test revealed a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85.

These three questionnaires were tested for validity by the three experts in the field. All of the experts agreed that the questionnaire is a strong and trustworthy tool for determining the interplay of stress, emotional intelligence, and work-life balance. Also, a pilot study was carried out with 15 ambulance staff (who were not included in the study sample) in order to assess the reliability of the questionnaires. The ambulance staff required fifteen to twenty minutes to complete the questionnaire.

The collected data were tabulated and analyzed using descriptive statistics like frequency distribution, mean, SD, and inferential statistics.

Research Ethics:

Every procedure was completed in compliance with all applicable rules and regulations, including the Helsinki Declaration. The study was approved by the King Khalid University Ethical Review Board (ECM#2023-1906). The participants were made aware of the objectives, risks, and advantages of the study and gave

their informed consent thereafter. Participants received the guarantee that their participation was completely voluntary and that they could withdraw at any time, for any reason. The anonymity and confidentiality of participants were maintained, and only aggregated data were utilized.

Results

	Characteristics	f	(%)
Gender	Male	27	15.8
	Female	144	84.2
Marital status	Single	102	59.6
	Married	65	38.0
	Divorced	4	2.4
Age	20-29	125	73.1
	30-39	43	25.1
	40-49	3	1.8
Level of Education	Diploma	52	30.4
	Undergraduate	34	19.9
	Postgraduate	85	49.7
Nursing Experience	1-2 Years	62	36.3
	3-4 Years	50	29.2
	5-9 Years	39	22.8
	>10 Years	20	11.7

Table 1 presents the sociodemographic characteristics of 171 nurses who participated in the study. The majority of respondents were female (84.2%) and single (59.6%). Most participants were aged 20–29 years (73.1%), followed by 30–39 years (25.1%). In terms of education, nearly half held postgraduate

qualifications (49.7%), while 30.4% had a diploma and 19.9% were undergraduates. Regarding professional experience, 36.3% had 1–2 years, 29.2% had 3–4 years, and 22.8% had 5–9 years of nursing experience, whereas 11.7% had more than 10 years of experience.

Awareness Item	Yes (%)	No (%)
Basic information about AI	95.3	4.7
Heard about AI use in the medical field	86.0	14.0
AI taught in undergraduate education	64.3	35.7
Encountered/used AI in clinical practice	74.3	25.7
Knowledge of machine learning	71.3	28.7
AI in nursing diagnosis (electronic systems)	64.3	35.7
Used AI for drug dose calculation	73.7	26.3

Table 2 shows that nurses demonstrated a high level of awareness about artificial intelligence (AI). Most participants had basic knowledge of AI (95.3%) and its use in healthcare (86.0%). Over half reported exposure to AI concepts in

education (64.3%) and clinical practice (74.3%). Awareness of machine learning (71.3%), AI-supported nursing diagnoses (64.3%), and AI use in drug dose calculations

(73.7%) further indicates growing integration of AI in nursing practice.

Table 3. Mean Scores of Nurses' Perception toward Artificial Intelligence (AI) (N = 171)

Category	Key Items (Summarized)	Mean ± SD
Perception of Nurses regarding AI	Positive views on AI usefulness, well-being, and societal benefits	3.69 ± 1.05
Concern & Risk of AI	Worries about control, errors, and future dangers	3.00 ± 1.19
Integration of AI in Workplace	Willingness to use AI, efficiency in routine tasks	3.12 ± 1.08
Ethical & Societal Implications	Views on AI being sinister, spying, or unethical use	2.83 ± 1.17

Table 3 presents the mean scores of nurses' perceptions toward artificial intelligence. Overall, nurses showed a positive perception of AI's usefulness (Mean = 3.69 ± 1.05), while concerns and risks (Mean = 3.00 ± 1.19) and workplace integration (Mean = 3.12 ± 1.08)

reflected moderate views. The ethical and societal implications of AI received relatively lower scores (Mean = 2.83 ± 1.17), indicating mixed opinions about its moral and social impact.

Table 4. Association of Nurses' Perception toward AI with Selected Demographic Variables (N = 171)

Variable	Negative (%)	Positive (%)	p-Value
Gender	14.7	85.3	0.574
Marital Status	14.6	85.4	0.599
Age	14.6	85.4	0.755
Education	14.6	85.4	0.285
Experience	15.7	84.3	0.044

Table 4 displays the association between nurses' perceptions of artificial intelligence and their demographic variables. Most respondents showed a positive perception across all categories, ranging from 84.3% to 85.4%.

Among the variables, nursing experience demonstrated a significant association (p = 0.044) with perception, while gender, marital status, age, and education showed no statistically significant relationship.

Table 5. Overall Attitude Level of Nurses toward Artificial Intelligence (N = 171)

Attitude Level (Cutoff Value)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
< 60	25	14.6	14.6
> 60	146	85.4	85.4
Total	171	100.0	100.0

Table 5 illustrates the overall attitude levels of nurses toward artificial intelligence. The majority of participants (85.4%) scored above the cutoff value of 60, indicating a positive attitude toward AI, while only 14.6% exhibited

a negative attitude. This suggests that most nurses hold a favorable perception of AI integration in healthcare practice.

Awareness Level	Criteria	Frequency	Percent
High Awareness	> 80%	90	52.6
Moderate Awareness	60-80%	26	15.2
Low Awareness	< 60%	55	32.2

Table 6 presents the overall awareness levels of nurses regarding artificial intelligence. More than half of the participants (52.6%) demonstrated high awareness, while 15.2% showed moderate awareness, and 32.2% had low awareness. These findings indicate that the majority of nurses possess a strong understanding of AI and its applications in healthcare.

Discussion:

This chapter discusses the findings of the study exploring nurses’ awareness and attitudes toward artificial intelligence (AI) at Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore. The study examined two central aspects: awareness—nurses’ knowledge and familiarity with AI technologies—and attitude, which reflects their perceptions and openness toward AI in healthcare. Both dimensions are critical in determining how readily AI can be integrated into nursing education and clinical environments.

The majority of participants were female (84%), which is higher than the 73% reported in a Saudi [1]. Most nurses were aged 20–29 years, representing a younger generation likely to be more accepting of new technologies. In contrast, another study reported half of their participants aged 30–39 years [2]. Almost half of the nurses in this study held postgraduate degrees, possibly contributing to their better understanding of AI. Differences in work experience also appeared to shape perceptions, as more experienced nurses may exhibit caution, while younger nurses tend to show enthusiasm toward innovation [3].

Findings revealed a moderate level of awareness regarding AI in healthcare. A large majority (95%) correctly identified the definition of AI—higher than the 70.9% [4]. Similarly, 86% were aware of AI’s applications in healthcare, exceeding the 67.3%

reported in the same study. Over half of the participants had encountered or used AI in clinical practice, greater than the 32.1% [5]. These results suggest that AI exposure among Pakistani nurses is increasing, possibly due to emerging AI-assisted tools in hospitals for diagnostics and patient management.

The majority of nurses expressed a positive attitude toward AI. About 64.9% found AI “exciting,” surpassing the 53% global enthusiasm rate [6]. This may relate to participants’ younger age and higher digital literacy. Moreover, more than half of the nurses believed AI could positively influence human well-being, aligning with findings [7]. Similarly, 50% believed AI would benefit society in the future, consistent with study of Nepal, where 40% shared the same view [8]. These findings reflect growing optimism about AI’s role in improving healthcare delivery.

Despite general optimism, several concerns emerged. About 45% of participants feared that AI might “take control of people,” echoing findings [9], where 63% of U.S. respondents supported a ban on highly autonomous AI. The lower concern rate in this study could stem from cultural differences and less media exposure to debates about AI autonomy.

Furthermore, 35.1% of nurses believed that AI systems make frequent errors, indicating skepticism about their reliability. Another study reported similar findings, where AI misdiagnosed 72 out of 100 pediatric cases in a JAMA Pediatrics study [10]. These results highlight the importance of maintaining human oversight and critical thinking when using AI-based systems in patient care.

Interestingly, more than one-third of nurses disagreed that AI is dangerous—contrary to the Paullet and Colleagues survey [11], where most Americans viewed AI as a threat. The difference may reflect regional perceptions; in Pakistan, AI is commonly associated with technological advancement rather than existential risk.

About 35.7% of nurses agreed that AI systems can outperform humans in some tasks, suggesting moderate confidence in AI's capabilities. Lai and colleagues estimated a 50% likelihood that AI would surpass human performance across all tasks within 45 years [12]. The gap between public and expert opinion could stem from differences in technical knowledge and exposure.

Additionally, 32.7% of participants believed organizations use AI unethically, lower than the global concern level of 60% [13]. Limited public discourse and regulatory oversight may contribute to this difference. This indicates the need for clear ethical frameworks and transparent policies in healthcare AI implementation.

The overall positive attitude (85.4%) found in this study is notably higher than the 76% among healthcare students and 65.4% among Egyptian nursing managers [14]. This difference likely reflects the younger, tech-savvy, and well-educated nurses' greater familiarity with digital tools and appreciation of AI's potential to enhance care quality.

Conclusion:

This study of 171 nurses at Fatima Memorial Hospital reveals strong openness toward AI, with 85.4% expressing positive attitudes, yet balanced by key concerns: 45% feared AI autonomy, 35.1% highlighted errors, 38% worried about surveillance, and 32.7% cited unethical use. These results reflect a cautious optimism—nurses recognize AI's potential but remain aware of its challenges. To ensure safe and effective adoption, healthcare institutions should provide practical AI training, establish clear ethical guidelines, and involve nurses in decision-making. Such measures will enable nursing professionals to leverage AI for improved efficiency and patient care while preserving trust and ethical integrity.

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